

Comparison of Sports Specific Personality Traits between Undergraduate Male and Female Physical Education Students

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18611096>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 16-01-2026

Published: 10-02-2026

Keywords:

Sports, personality, traits, physical education, students.

ABSTRACT

The present study compares the *sports specific personality traits of undergraduate male and female physical education students*. The participants were a group of physical education students (N = 60) from Colleges affiliated to Manipur University such as Biramangol College, Naorem Birahari College, Kamakhya Pemton College, Universal College, T.S.Paul Manipur Womens's College. The tool used was a 100-item questionnaire developed by Dr. Agya Jit Singh and Dr. H.S. Cheema (2010). The objective of the study was to analyse the *comparison of sports specific personality traits between undergraduate male and female physical education students. It was hypothesised that physical education students might have a significant difference in their sports specific personality traits according to the gender they belong to. The data were analysed by using independent t-test with the help of IBM SPSS Statistics Version 22.* The results show male physical education students exhibit better sports specific personality than their female counterparts.

1.1 Introduction

Personality is the dynamic organisation of interlocking behaviour systems that each of us possesses as we

develop from a biological new-born to a bio-social adult in a world of other people and cultured products. The human personality is a marvellously intricate structure, a dedicated woven of motives, emotions, habits, and thoughts into a pattern that balances, however precariously, the pulls and pushes of the world outside. Personality is the total sum of "being" and includes physical, mental, social, emotional, and intellectual aspects. One's personality reflects his perception, imagination, attitude, instincts, habits, values, interests, and sentiments about himself and his self-worth. Intelligence, achievement, motivation, modes of adjustment Perception is the product of biological and cultural heritage. A child is born with some biological heritage, while the cultural environment moulds and shapes his personality. Personality is in fact a product of the interaction of a biological organism with the social environment. In other words, personality is the way an individual adjusts to his external environment. It is his way of responding to the environment. Therefore, the key to personality development is socialization, where biology and culture merge. Personality reveals the psychological make-up of an individual through his behaviour. In fact, it is the quality of a person's total behaviour. Personality is a dynamic and continuous process of learning in which the individual acquires the typical modes of response. The word "personality" is used to subsume all the factors, inherited or acquired, which make up an individual. It is the total sum of what one is, one's typical response patterns and behaviour patterns (Ajmer et al., 2017). Personality is understood as a theoretical construct, aimed at describing, explaining, and predicting the ways of human beings and functioning in various aspects of life. Various personality concepts consider the individual differences in the cognitive and social context of the various psychological paradigms. Theories based on the feature concept have contributed significantly to the development of personality research. The five-factor personality model includes scales describing the basic personality traits: neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. These features are biologically determined and are subject to environmental influences. Personality traits of a healthy individual contribute to shaping one's self-image, attitudes, personal goals, and self-confidence, as well as determining how to adapt to changing environmental conditions (Costa and McCrae, 1992).

1.2. The Objective and Research Hypotheses

The objective of the study was to analyze the difference in sports specific personality test of physical education students according to their gender.

Therefore, this research hypothesized that physical education students might have a significant difference in their Sports Specific Personality Test according to the gender they belong to.

1.3 Materials and Methods

1.3.1 The Participants

The questionnaire was completed by 60 physical education students (30 males and 30 females) from different universities and colleges. The age of the participants ranged from 17 to 25 years. In terms of sample distribution by institution, 12 were from Biramangol College, 12 from Naorem Birahari College, 12 from K.P. College, 12 from Universal College and 12 from T.S.Paul Manipur Womens College. The Snow-ball sampling technique was used while recruiting participants for the study. All participants had been undergoing graduate course at the time of data collection.

1.3.2 Data Collection

Data collection occurred over a span of two months . The research was based on responses from a sample of physical education students (N = 60), from different colleges. We cannot rule out the possibility of selection bias. However, the characteristics of the surveyed academics adequately represent those of the population as a whole in terms of characteristics such as gender of participants.

1.3.3 Instrument

The instrument used was the sports-specific personality test standardized by Dr. Agya Jit Singh and Dr. H.S. Cheema, 2010. The primary investigator first approached various physical education students, male and female, from the various colleges in Manipur Valley. Permission was taken from all the participants while collecting the data from them. Proper instructions were given for filling out the questionnaire and rapport was established properly. The Sports Specific Personality Test (SSPT) was administered through self-administration. Scoring was done as per the sports-specific personality test manual, and the results were statistically analyzed. The questionnaire's responses are composed of a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 "always", 2 "often", 3 "sometimes", and 4 "never".

1.3.4 Results

Gender and Sports Specific Personality Test

H_a: Physical education students might have a significant difference in their Sports Specific Personality Test according to the gender they belong to.

Table 1

The significant mean difference in sports specific personality traits between male and female physical education students

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	SEM	t	p-value
Male	30	85.07	8.15	1.488	-3.47	0.001
Female	30	91.87	6.99	1.276		

*significant at 0.05 level

Source: computed from field survey data

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviation values for male and female physical education students for the Sports Specific Personality Test were (M = 85.07, SD = 8.15) and (M = 91.87, SD = 6.99), respectively. The results indicate a significant difference between male and female in Sports Specific Personality Test, t = -3.47, p = 0.001. The hypothesis was retained. It was inferred that male have higher level of sports specific personality than female counterparts.

Figure: 1

MEAN COMPARISON ON SPORTS SPECIFIC PERSONALITY TRAITS BETWEEN UNDERGRADUATE MALE AND FEMALE PHYSICAL EDUCATION

1.3.6 Discussion

Our finding indicated a significant difference in the Sports Specific Personality trait between male and female physical education students. Male physical education students scored higher than their female counterparts as measured by the sports-specific personality test of Dr. Agya Jit Singh and Dr. H.S.

Cheema (2010). Our finding is in line with other studies (Anjanabai & Chandrappa, 2017; Kuloor, 2017). However, our finding is in contrast to Parmar and Desai (2020) finding.

1.3.7 Conclusion

The conclusion was drawn that male physical education students possess high of male participation develops and sport-specific personality traits compared to their counterparts. It was rationalised that the nature nurtures the sport-specific personality values and character among the participating physical education students.

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